

**E5.3 Intermediate prototype
for data aggregation for self-
optimization processes on
network operations**
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**Programa de Universalización de
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List of Acronyms

3D	Three Dimension
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOps	AI Operations
AR	Augmented Reality
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
6DoF	Six Degrees of Freedom
FPS	Frame per Second
HD	High Definition
HTC	Holographic-Type Communications
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NR	New Radio
QoE	Quality of Experience
RAN	Radio Access Network
SoA	State-of-the-Art
TD	Technological Domain
UE	User Equipment
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

1 Introduction

Data aggregation for self-optimization processes in network operations refers to the process of collecting and combining data from various sources within a network environment to improve its efficiency, performance, and reliability. This data aggregation process involves gathering data from different network devices, such as routers, switches, and servers, as well as monitoring tools and sensors deployed throughout the network infrastructure.

Once the data is collected, it is aggregated and analyzed to identify patterns, trends, and anomalies that may indicate areas for optimization or improvement within the network. This analysis can include assessing network traffic patterns, identifying bottlenecks or congestion points, monitoring resource utilization, and detecting security threats or vulnerabilities. Based on the insights gained from the data analysis, self-optimization processes can be implemented to automatically adjust network configurations, allocate resources more efficiently, optimize traffic routing, and proactively address issues to enhance overall network performance and reliability.

By using data aggregation and self-optimization techniques, it is possible to ensure that network infrastructure operates at peak performance levels, adapts to changing conditions, and meets the evolving demands of users and applications. This ultimately leads to a more agile, resilient, and cost-effective network environment. In this regard, the confidence level is one metric that can help the Machine Learning models that are in charge of the optimization techniques to help them make decisions. A confidence level refers to the degree of certainty or trustworthiness associated with the predictions made by the model. It represents the model's estimation of how accurate or reliable its predictions are for a given input data point. A higher confidence level indicates greater certainty in the prediction, while a lower confidence level suggests more uncertainty.

Confidence levels are typically expressed as probabilities or percentages, representing the likelihood that a prediction falls within a certain range of outcomes. These probabilities are often derived from the model's internal mechanisms, such as confidence scores assigned to individual predictions or confidence intervals calculated based on the model's performance on training and validation data.

Understanding the confidence level of a machine learning model's predictions is crucial for decision-making and risk assessment in real-world applications. It helps users gauge the reliability of the model's outputs and determine the appropriate actions to take based on the level of confidence associated with each prediction. Additionally, monitoring and adjusting the confidence threshold can enable users to customize the model's behavior to meet specific performance and reliability requirements for different applications.

2 Conceptual description

Data aggregation is key when analyzing the trends and behaviors of the network. However, due to the massive amount of data, it is necessary to perform a statistical analysis rather than a specific one. Statistical aggregation is essential in data analysis for summarizing large datasets into manageable decisions and identifying patterns and trends. By condensing data at different levels of granularity, such as time intervals or geographic regions, analysts can uncover valuable insights that drive decision-making. Aggregating data also enables comparisons between groups or categories, helping to compare performance and identify outliers. Moreover, aggregation helps reduce noise and variability in the data, making it easier to discern underlying signals. Visualizations of aggregated data, such as charts and graphs, are powerful tools for communicating findings to stakeholders and decision-makers, facilitating understanding and informed decision-making processes. The statistical technique that we used in 6G-ENABLERS for data aggregation for self-optimization processes on network operations is called statistical aggregation based on Cumulative Distribution Function (CFD).

3 Configuration and usage

Statistical aggregation based on cumulative distribution function (CDF) is a powerful technique used in data analysis to distill large datasets into meaningful insights. By leveraging CDF, analysts can summarize data at different levels of granularity, such as time intervals or geographic regions, to uncover patterns and trends. This approach enables the identification of key metrics and distributions within the data, facilitating comparisons between groups or categories and the detection of outliers. Moreover, aggregating data using CDF helps reduce noise and variability, making it easier to discern underlying patterns and relationships.

We have implemented the statistical distribution aggregation through the following pseudo code logic:

```
function sla_loss(x_data, lower_bound):
    x = create_variable("x", x_data) # Create a variable representing the input data
    pred = apply_function(f, x) # Predict values using function f
    pred_values = extract_values(pred) # Extract values from the predictions
    dist = create_empirical_distribution(pred_values) # Create an empirical distribution
    cdf = calculate_cdf(dist, lower_bound) # Calculate the CDF at the lower bound
    return cdf
```

The `sla_loss` function is designed to calculate the CDF of a set of predicted values generated by our machine learning model. First, the input data `x_data` is passed to the function, representing the features used for prediction. These features are encapsulated within a variable `x` to facilitate further computation. Next, the function `f` is applied to the input variable `x` to generate predictions. These predictions are then extracted into a separate array `pred_values` for further analysis. Utilizing the extracted prediction values, an empirical distribution is created to model the distribution of the predictions. Subsequently, the CDF of this empirical distribution is calculated at a specified lower bound. Finally, the computed CDF value is returned as the output of the `sla_loss` function. Overall, this function provides a convenient and efficient way to assess the distributional properties of predicted values and evaluate model performance based on predefined criteria. The results are showed in the following graph:

Figure 1 Cumulative distributed Function results.

For the complete code of the Pipelines, please refer to the respective GitLab repository:

https://gitlab.i2cat.net/rdprojects/6genablers/6genablers-ai/kubeflow-pipelines/-/blob/main/pipeline_6g.py

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, in optimization models for telecommunication networks, the need for statistical aggregation based on cumulative distribution function (CDF) arises from the inherent complexity and variability of network traffic and resource utilization patterns. Traditional optimization approaches often rely on deterministic assumptions or simplified statistical models, which may not accurately capture the stochastic nature of network behavior. By using statistical aggregation techniques based on CDF, optimization models can account for the full range of possible outcomes and uncertainties in network conditions, leading to more robust and reliable performance predictions.

Furthermore, statistical aggregation based on CDF enables optimization models to incorporate probabilistic constraints and objectives, allowing for more flexible and adaptive network management strategies. By quantifying the probability of meeting certain performance targets or constraints, operators can make informed decisions to optimize resource allocation, routing, and scheduling policies in telecommunication networks. Ultimately, statistical aggregation based on CDF empowers optimization models to achieve better alignment with real-world network dynamics and improve the overall efficiency, reliability, and quality of service in telecommunication systems.